

A Review Paper on VK Mart Application

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Abstract:- This system app involves the client, retailer, products. presently the merchandising assiduity is roaring assiduity in India. It has been considered as equal competent with IT assiduity. VK Mart is notorious for its low price and good quality products. Merchandising is one similar step in the marketing chain of conditioning that facilitates the distribution function. So, merchandising desisted to be considered as an outgrowth of traditional marketing exertion, rather it was honored as an important business proposition in its own accord, VK Mart eventually helps marketing in performing its function and successfully satisfying the objects. The objects of the study are to understand client satisfaction towards colorful products vended by VK MART and also assay the satisfaction position of client experience while shopping at VK MART. Peoples are get attracted towards the online shopping. VK MART is one similar big retail mammoth that has a wide request with varity of product lines. The findings and suggestions handed in the exploration study will clearly help VK MART to make necessary changes to give enhanced guests to its guests in the said outlet. There are numerous different varieties of the products like eating particulars, groceries, implements, clothes, shoes, etc.

Keywords:- Component; Formatting; Style; Styling; Insert.

I. INTRODUCTION

The title of our project is “VK Mart App”. This project will handle all the online retailing activities of the mart .The online shopping has become effective facility that a modern society requires .It provides facilities such as ordering items online, provides various varieties of shopping items like various brands of rice, tea, coffee, etc . There are various sections for kids, adults, grocery, shoes, cloths, and other such things. Expanding facilities, choosing showcase shares, creating advancement client benefits and delivering items speedily are just a few of the organizational functions

conceivable through our app. It includes all aspects of an organization’s electronic intelligence with partners, who determine the organization’s future. It is an online marketplace that facilitates trade between suppliers, resellers and customers, with heavy reliance of external social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram.

II. OBJECTIVES

The template is used to format your paper and style the text. All margins, column widths, line spaces, and text fonts are prescribed; please do not alter them. You may note peculiarities. For example, the head margin in this template measures proportionately more than is customary. This measurement and others are deliberate, using specifications that anticipate your paper as one part of the entire proceedings, and not as an independent document. Please do not revise any of the current designations. The objectives of this system are: i. To analyse the customer satisfaction towards the products sold by VK Mart. ii. To analyse the satisfaction level of customer experience while shopping at VK Mart. The main objective is to fulfill the needs of the customers whatever their requirements are. iii. VK Mart focuses on fulfilling the needs of the customer on the exact time. VK Mart provides all the produtes which customers are in need. The main purpose of the VK Mart is to supply the unique things which are mostly not available in the another shops.

III. LITRETAURE REVIEW

A. D Mart (Kale Padal Road Hadapsar):

This D Mart is established in the year 2013. The pin code of Kale Padal Road, Hadapsar is 411028. The store is spread over a large with the groceries in the ground floor, apparels and footwear and curtains, toys, steel utensils and home appliances also. This mart had completed the 10 years, the timing of open until 11:00 pm. In this mart various categories are included like women, kids, men. All things are

available in this d mart. Food items are also included. This d mart provides online services in specific area. Sometimes it shows the error in online shopping, sometimes there are some delivery problems. They provides the services like shop in store, same day delivery. In this d mart the mode of payments are cash, visa card, master card, debit card, credit card . If any source of payment is not working then the remaining modes are available for the customer. The opening time of this d mart is at 10:00 am. This d mart is open from Monday to Sunday means for a whole week. There are many offers were given by this d mart. At various festivals there are big offers were given to the customer. At Diwali they gave 50% off. It has wide range of products and services to cater to the varied requirements of their customers.

The equations are an exception to the specified specifications of this template. You'll need to determine whether or not your equation should be compartmented using either the Established in the time 2014, D Mart in the Rankala, Kolhapur is a top player in the order supermarkets in the Kolhapur. This well- known establishment acts as a one stop destination servicing both original and from other corridor of Kolhapur. Over the course of this trip, this business has established a establishment base in its assiduity. The belief that client satisfaction is an important as their products and services, have helped this establishment garner a vast base of guests, which nonstop to grow by the day. This business employs individualities that are devoted towards their separate places and put in a lot of trouble to achieve the common vision and larger pretensions of the company.

In the near future, this business aims to expand its line of product and services and cater to a larger client base. This D Mart opens at 8:00 am to 10:00 pm . It is open from Monday to Sunday means for whole it is available. In Kolhapur, this establishment occupies a prominent location in Rankala. It is at Phulewadi Road , Opposite Rankala Talav, which makes it easy for first-time visitors in locating this establishment

B. D Mart (Tarabai Park , Kolhapur):

This D Mart opens at 11:00 am to 10:00 pm . It is open from Monday to Sunday means for whole it is available. In Kolhapur, this establishment occupies a prominent location in Tarabai Park. Established in the year 2009. It is known to provide top service in the following categories: Readyment Garments Retailers, Departmental Stores, Shoe Dealers, Sports Goods Dealers, Saree Retailers, Dairy Product Retailers, Fabric Retailers. It is at , Near Tarabai Park & Sadar Bazaar, Sasane Ground. The peoples who are visiting first time to D Mart will becomes easy to find out the address. It has a wide range of products and services to fulfill the need or requirements of their customers.

C. Amazon

Amazon was innovated on July 5, 1994, by Jeff Bezos, who chose the Seattle area for its cornucopia of specialized gift, as Microsoft was in the area. Amazon.com is an e-commerce platform that sells numerous product lines, including media(books, pictures, music, and software),

vesture, baby products, consumer electronics, beauty products, epicure food, groceries, health and particular care products, artificial & scientific inventories, kitchen particulars, jewelry, watches, field and theater particulars, musical instruments, sporting goods, tools, automotive particulars, toys and games, and ranch inventories and consulting services. Amazon.com is primarily a retail point with a deals profit model; Amazon takes a small chance of the trade price of each item that's vended through its website while also allowing companies to announce their products by paying to be listed as featured products. Amazon allows druggies to submit reviews to the web runner of each product. pundits must rate the product on a standing scale from one to five stars. Amazon provides a badging option for pundits which indicates the real name of the critic(grounded on evidence of a credit card account) or which indicates that the critic is one of the top pundits by fashion ability. Amazon has a number of products and services available, including its digital adjunct Alexa, Amazon Music and Prime Video for music and vids independently, the Amazon Appstore for Android apps, and its Kindle tackle line of e-readers and tablets. Audible provides audiobooks for purchase and listening. In September 2021, Amazon blazoned the launch of Astro, its first ménage robot, powered by its Alexa smart home technology. This can be remote- controlled when not at home, to check on faves , people, or home security. It'll shoot possessors a announcement if it detects commodity unusual. Amazon Web Services(AWS) is a attachment of that provides on demand pall calculating platforms and APIs to individualities, companies, and governments, on a metered pay- as- you- go base. These pall calculating web services give distributed computing processing capacity and software tools via AWS garçon granges. As of 2021 Q4, AWS has 33 request share for pall structure while the coming two challengers Microsoft Azure and Google Cloud have 21, and 10 independently, according to Synergy Group.

D. Flipkart:

Flipkart Private Limited is an Indian e-commerce company established in 2007. It started with a primary focus on online book deals and soon, expanded to life products, electronics, home rudiments and groceries. moment, Flipkart is the biggest online Indian business contending with the world leader Amazon. It's one of the most popular online commerce in India. Sachin Bansal and Binny Bansal established thee-commerce business as an online bookshop. still, as the company's character rose, it developed and broadened its range of services to meet its adding client base. The first month of business was October 2007, and Bengaluru was chosen as the position for the company's headquarters. In addition to dealing books, the platform began offering a wide range of other effects, including music, mobile phones, and other electronic bias, because-commerce is precipitously bringing about a change in the world of retail and is gaining instigation in India, Flipkart has evolved at a quick rate and continuously added several new item orders to its collection.

E. Summary

The thing of this exploration was to produce a VK Mart App design system. This system app involves the customer, retailer, products. The purpose of this app is to give the online products to the guests. Peoples can order the product sitting in the home. From this app guests can place the order, by this the time isn't wasted and they can do their remaining work. still, log in to the separate online delivery VK Mart app to order, and also admit their order in just the coming couple of twinkles, If peoples want any thing also they only need is to pick up their smartphone. This process is so simple and comforting. In this app the prints of all the products are also available, because of this the guests can fluently find out the effects and get those effects. furnishing home delivery is the main task or purpose of this app.

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

To help the customers the requirements should be understood by the sellers. All the record of the customers should be register. They have to understand the basic needs of the customers. Which things are in the trending, should be understood. The customer satisfaction about there products are very important. The most important thing is the quality and brand so the product must have of quality because if the product is not of quality then customer will not satisfied with it.

The most important thing is communication with the customer. The needs should get properly understood by the owner. VK Mart management involves lots of communication and collaboration. Administrators, owners, customers, have to be able to talk within their groups and also with each other.

V. METHODOLOGY

We have created the online shopping app. In this app the , first login page is available to user login . Our online VK Mart app is very useful for the users. Our app saves the time of the user. By using online reference we created this app. This online shopping app is very beneficial for the peoples. The main purpose of creating this online app to provide the online service to the users.

VI. PROJECT SCOPE

In today's world, online facilities are not limited operations, but rather, the administrators have been hoping for an advanced system. This online app is proposed for the full of benefits. Nowadays peoples are get attracted towards the online shopping so this app will also become in the trending manner. This project can fulfil the needs of customers, saves the time, there will not any wastage of time.

Fig 1 :- DFD Level 2

This online app provides various facilities to the peoples. In the very short period of time customers were satisfied. This project is very helpful in the future, it is created on the basis of future focus. The trend of this world is of online trend, there are not many online shopping mart, our project wil provides online material.

VII. CONCLUSION

VK Mart app has a very unique way of operating the business model also it has managed to save lots of money by various strategies along with saving money they have managed to beat the competitors in market. It's time to reduce the stress of the customers by giving them online shopping service ,the VK Mart app help them for doing online shopping. From this project we are going to provide the online products and focuses on the requirements of the people that how to make easy for them. By taking all the information from the VK Mart we make this project. We learn various things from this project. VK Mart have so many product which are very useful in day to day life. From this project we learn that how to manage the app, we experience a lots of things. We learn what are the actual needs of the peoples. On the basis of the peoples need we develop this VK Mart app.

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